

Profitability Analysis of ESAF Micro Finance Bank

Vishnu V S

M.Com (Net)

Corresponding Author- Vishnu V S

Email: vishmusvalliyil@gmail.com

Abstract:

This study focuses on investigation of the profitability and liquidity position of ESAF MICROFINANCE BANK. This analysis is done using various ratios such as Cash Position Ratio, Current Ratio, Debt Equity Ratio. Also used trend analysis on Net profit & Interest Spread. Official website of the said bank was the source of data for the last five years' annual reports. The analysis helps to evaluate the performance of the bank.

Key Words: Cash Position Ratio, Current Ratio, Debt Equity Ratio, Trend Analysis

Introduction: Economic development of a nation is in part dependent on the performance of private sector banks. Micro finance banks play crucial role in the economic growth. Small Finance Banks helps the growth of nation. They're known as niche banks. Financial inclusion of different sectors of the economy, especially those not covered by other banks, which includes but not limited to small businesses operating regionally and small and verging farmers in the rural areas and unorganized sector entities is the primary objective of small finance banks.

ESAF aims to serve the sectors not covered by the other banks. Over last few years growth of ESAF small finance bank is exceptional. In 1995 it started operations as a Micro Enterprises Developmental service. On October 2015, Reserve Bank of India issued principle license to ESAF to setup a small finance bank. ESAF small finance bank is operating with 550 banking outlets which are diversified across 19 states and 2 Union Territories as on March 31, 2021. Ratio analysis means analysis and interpretation of the figures appearing in the financial statement. Trend analysis is used to analyses (Net Profit, Interest Spread) whether increasing trend or decreasing trend over the last five years. Ratio analysis is most appropriate tool used for measuring the performance of any organization. Profitability and liquidity position of ESAF micro finance bank can be estimated by using ratio analysis.

Literature Review

Gupta (2014) in his article titled "An empirical study of financial performance of ICICI bank - a comparative analysis focused on operational control profitability and solvency etc.," has examined and compared the performance of ICICI bank in matters pertaining to financial aspects. He has also suggested certain modifications through which the bank can improve upon its efficiency.

Jaiswal and Jain (2016) have authored an article titled "A comparative study of financial performance of SBI and ICICI Bank in India". In

this article the authors have tried to assess the financial performance of two of the most reputed Indian banks with the help of CAMEL Model. This financial performance of SBI and ICICI are compared from the financial years 2010-11 to 2014-15.

Mukhopadhyay k (2000) has tried to analyse the challenges being faced by public sector banks on the initiation of reform measures. The paper observed that Public Sector Banks are already being marginalised by the private counterparts and the challenges are forecasted to only increase further.

Tirkeyi and Salem (2013) have investigated the financial positions of ICICI and HDFC banks by making use of their financial statements and incorporating the technique of ratio analysis by adapting different ratios. Based on their study, they were able to concluded that ICICI bank faired higher than HDFC bank in terms of financial position.

Uppal and Kaur (2007) found that banks of foreign origin are in tussle with private sector banks that are recently established by adapting improved technologies for betterment of their performance.

Vinod Kumar and Bhawna Malhotra (2017) have attempted for performance evaluation & financial levelheadedness of few of the top private sector banks in India using CAMEL approach. The study looked into the data available between FY 2007 to 2017. The authors ranked Axis Bank at the top and ICICI bank stood second. The list was followed by Kotak Mahindra Bank and HDFC Bank which stood third and fourth respectively. However, IndusInd bank bottomed the list amongst the banks that the authors had considered for the purpose of this study.

Research Design: Our current work chiefly relies on secondary data and is primarily expository in nature. Annual reports over the last five years of the bank selected are the primary source of reference for our study. The data is analyzed to measure the liquidity position as well as profitability position of ESAF micro finance bank. The variable used for the study are the following

3.1 Cash Position Ratio (CPR)

“Absolute Liquidity Ratio” is the measure of the liquidity of cash and near cash items appearing in the balance sheet.

3.2 Current Ratio (CR)

Current Ratio depicts the pertinence between current assets and current liabilities. The assets that can be liquefied into cash within 1 year are referred to as current assets. The arrearage which is supposed to be cleared within 1 year are known as current liabilities.

3.3 Debt-Equity Ratio (DER)

Debt-Equity Ratio is also known as the gearing ratio. It assesses the relationship between shareholders fund and debt. It indicates proportion of the shareholder’s equity and the debt used to finance the assets. High debt equity ratio means creditors claim over the assets and which is unfavorable. Low debt equity ratio means lesser claim on assets by the creditors.

3.4 Net Interest Rate Spread (NIRS)

The disparity between the interest rate that a financial institution is offering as interest on

deposits and the rate of interest that it charges the borrowers is known as net interest rate spread. It is used to measure profitability of the financial institution. The favorable position means interest received from customers should be always higher than the interest rate given to the depositors.

3.5 Net Profit (NP)

Net Profit simply means a firm’s total earnings after deducting total expenses. Net profit is the determination of profit of a firm by subtracting all revenue expenses from the revenue earnings. In case of a financial institution, it is equal to a total interest income minus total interest expenses.

Results and Discussion:

4.1 Cash position Ratio

Cash position Ratio can be obtained using the formula

$$\text{Cash Position Ratio} = \frac{\text{Cash and Bank Balances} + \text{Marketable Securities}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

Ideally the cash position ratio should be 0.75:1

Table 1: Cash Position Ratio of ESAF Small Finance Bank

Year	CPR
2016	0.33
2017	2.64
2018	0.93
2019	1.76
2020	2.36

Table 1, explains the ability to the financial obligations of the bank. The CPR was .033 on 2016 and it shows an upward growth in other years except in 2018. The CPR was high in 2017 with 2.64% which decreased by 1.71% in 2018. But it increased

in the coming years, which is a positive sign. Since the ideal ratio is 0.75:1.

4.2 Current Ratio

Current Ratio can be obtained using the formula

$$\text{Current Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

Ideal Ratio is 2:1

Table 2: Current Ratio of ESAF Small Finance Bank

Year	CR
2016	1.64
2017	1.69
2018	0.47
2019	0.88
2020	1.56

Table 2, shows the current ratio of 2016 is 1.64% and increased a little in 2017. But in 2017 it decreased to 047% in 2018. It shows increasing trend in 2019 & 2020 but still less than the ideal ratio. It needs more focus.

Ideal Ratio is = Less than 1

4.3 Debt-Equity Ratio (DER)

Debt-Equity Ratio can be obtained using the formula

$$\text{Debt-Equity Ratio} = \frac{\text{Shareholders Funds}}{\text{Total Long-Term Funds}}$$

Table 3: Debt-Equity Ratio of ESAF Small Finance Bank

Year	DER
2016	0.43
2017	0.14
2018	0.20
2019	0.52
2020	0.90

Table 3, shows the debt equity ratio. In 2016 is 0.43% which is good for the bank. In 2017 it very low indicate low dependence on long term funds. In 2018 & 2019 it is lower than 1. So, it is favorable to the bank. In 2020 Debt-Equity Ratio reached 0.90 which is close to 1 and the bank needs to control

long term funds to maintain good financial position for future growth.

4.4 Net Interest Rate Spread (NIRS)

Net Interest Rate Spread can be obtained using the formula

$$NET\ INTEREST\ RATE\ SPREAD = INTEREST\ RECEIVED - INTEREST\ EXPENDED$$

Table 4: Net Interest Rate Spread of ESAF Small Finance Bank

<i>Year</i>	<i>NIRS</i>
2016	154962136
2017	132823933
2018	2820194843
2019	5733568075
2020	7921881

The table 4, shows net interest rate spread. In 2016 interest rate received is higher than interest rate expended. Every year it shows positive sign and indicate profitability of ESAF micro finance bank.

Though the net interest rate spread in 2020 is lower than 2019 still favorable to the firm. The

positive growth rate is indicating good profitability position of the firm.

4.5 Net Profit (NP)

Net Profit can be obtained using the formula

$$NET\ PROFIT = TOTL\ INCOME - TOTAL\ EXPENSES$$

Table 5: Net Profit of ESAF Small Finance Bank

<i>Year</i>	<i>NP</i>
2016	340074319
2017	7629557
2018	269948648
2019	902838321
2020	1903898000

Table 5, shows steady and healthy net profit over last five years. In 2017 net profit decreased than in 2016. But in coming years net profit increased every year. High net profit indicates the bank is able to control its overall and expenses at the same was able to increase its earnings, which shows a positive sign for the growth of the bank.

Conclusion: ESAF Small Finance Bank is lending loans lower and middle income groups and is offering associated services within the territorial regions of India. Its headquarters is in Thrissur. It offers all kinds of banking services including modern services like ATMs, Debit Card, Safe Deposit Lockers, Internet Banking, Mobile Banking, Agent banking, SMS Banking, RTGS, NEFT, CTS etc. This study aims to find out the financial position of ESAF Small Finance Bank from the annual reports published on its website. Tools used for the analysis are Cash Position Ratio, Current Ratio, Debt- Equity Ratio, Net Interest Rate Spread, Net Profit. Cash Position Ratio shows fluctuations in the beginning and later shows good results. Current Ratio doesn't seem to meet the ideal standard. The bank needs to focus on its current assts to meet the liquidity position for future growth. Debt-Equity Ratio shows good financial position of the bank. Net Interest Rate Spread during the period of study shows steady and positive sign which indicate the profitability of the bank. Net Profit also shows good results over the last five years. The ESAF Small Finance Bank needs more attention on its current assets. The ratio between current assets and liabilities

indicates low liquidity position during the period of study. The bank should invest more on its current assets to maintain good liquidity position.

References

- (n.d.). Retrieved from www.esafbank.com.
- Gupta. (2014). An Empirical Study of Financial Performance of ICCI Bank-A Comparative Analysis. IITM Journal of Business Studies(JBS),(1)1.
- Jaiswal and Jain . (2016). A Comparative Study of Financial Performance of SBI and ICCI Banks in India. International Journal of Scientific Research in Computer Science and Engineering , 1-6.
- K, M. (2000). Challenges Before the Public Sector in the Next Millennium, Monthly Review. SBI Monthly Review:Vol.XXXIX,No.1, 26-33.
- Tirkeyi and Salem . (2013). A Comparative Study of Financial Statement of ICCI and HDFC Through Ratio Analysis. International Journal of Accounting and Financial Mangement Research(IJAFMR), 89-96.
- Uppal, R K and Kaur . (2007). Indian Banking Sector: Efficiency in the Post-Banking Sector Reforms Era- New Challenges and Future Opportunities. Prestige Journal of Bank Management and Research, 42-55.
- Vinod Kumar and Bhawna Malhotra . (2017). A Camel Model Analysis of Private Banks in India. International Journal of Economic and Business Review:Volume-5,Issue -7, 87-93.